

Advanced Modeling of Non-Spherical Biomass Particle Motion in Suspension Combustion

Jingliang Wang(汪靖良)^a, Qingyan Fang (方庆艳)^{a*}, Cheng Zhang (张成)^a, Chungen Yin (殷春根)^{b*}

^aState Key Laboratory of Coal Combustion, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Wuhan, 430000;

^bAAU Energy Aalborg University, Aalborg East, Denmark, 9220;

*State Key Laboratory of Coal Combustion, Huazhong University of Science and Technology, Wuhan, 430000, China (Qingyan Fang). E-mail address: qyfang@hust.edu.cn

*Department of Energy Technology, Aalborg University, 9220 Aalborg East, Denmark, (Chungen Yin). E-mail address: chy@et.aau.dk

ABSTRACT: To address the aerodynamic differences encountered during the co-firing of straw biomass particles in coal-fired power plants, this work extends the conventional modeling framework for dilute multiphase particle motion and proposes a novel, closed model for non-spherical particle dynamics and combustion. The model incorporates generalized correlations derived from previous particle-resolved direct numerical simulations and systematically accounts for drag, lift, pressure gradient force, virtual mass force, and torque induced rotational motion experienced by realistic cylindrical particles under various flow conditions. These aerodynamic effects are effectively coupled with an optimized combustion model, enabling high-fidelity simulation of both translational and rotational particle dynamics. Numerical simulations conducted in a 10 meter long biomass co-firing burner validate the model of accuracy and broad applicability

24 in predicting non-spherical particle trajectories, residence time, temperature evolution, and burnout
25 performance. Results show that, compared to the conventional equivalent volume spherical particle
26 model, the proposed novel model increases the average particle residence time by 20.21% and the
27 average particle temperature by 28.31%. This promotes a more rapid release of volatiles and
28 enhanced char oxidation, thereby improving the overall combustion efficiency of biomass particles.
29 Under sufficient oxygen conditions, the combination of extended residence time and elevated
30 particle temperatures facilitates more complete combustion of large biomass particles. Consequently,
31 the proposed model demonstrates strong potential for simulating particle laden multiphase flows in
32 engineering applications and serves as a powerful numerical tool for achieving efficient biomass
33 co-firing utilization in coal-fired boilers.

34 **KEY WORDS:** non-spherical particles; drag , lift, and torque correlations; closed model; biomass
35 suspension combustion; computational fluid dynamics

37 **1 Introduction**

38 The escalating threats of climate change and fossil fuel depletion have propelled the
39 widespread adoption of renewable energies ¹. Biomass is one of the most abundant renewable
40 energy sources, and is commonly coupled with coal-fired boilers in thermochemical conversion
41 processes ² to ensure sustainability and provide economic benefits ³. Against the backdrop of the
42 "dual-carbon" targets , an increasing number of power plants are incorporating biomass co-firing,
43 leading to rapid reductions in CO₂ emissions, along with more efficient processes and various
44 environmental advantages ⁴. Biomass combustion commonly employs the suspension combustion
45 technology owing to its high combustion efficiency, thorough mixing, and short residence times ⁵.
46 However, each phase of this process possesses diverse scientific and technological challenges ⁶

47 related to the gas phase, the particle phase, and the turbulent flow ⁷.

48 When designing combustors for co-firing biomass, conventional coal powder burner designs
49 often cannot be directly applied ⁸. This is due to the unique properties of biomass raw materials and
50 the preparation methods used by power plants. Consequently, the biomass particles for heating and
51 power generation are typically larger, less dense, and non-spherically shaped ⁶. The most commonly
52 used biomass for co-firing is straw, which is typically pulverised to produce cylindrical straw
53 particles with an average diameter of ~2 mm and an average length of ~20 mm, although individual
54 particles can reach up to 150 mm in length (see Fig. 1) ⁹. In contrast, coal powder particles are
55 smaller, with an average diameter of only 75 μm . Thus, when carrying out computational fluid
56 dynamics (CFD) numerical simulations, the prevailing models for tracking the solid particle phases
57 present in dilute multiphase flows rely on a Lagrangian framework with point-like spherical
58 particles ¹⁰. Typically, only the drag and gravity are considered ⁷, and the particle motion models
59 solve only the translational motion equations, which are overly simplistic in the context of large,
60 irregular, and non-spherical biomass particles. Consequently, such models are unsuitable for
61 application to straw particles. As previously reported, significant differences in the particle size and
62 shape greatly influence the motion and conversion characteristics of biomass particles in a
63 combustion furnace, wherein the gas – solid two-phase flow has a tremendous impact on the overall
64 boiler performance ⁹. It is therefore necessary to accurately simulate the trajectories of large,
65 irregular, and non-spherical biomass particles to simulate the entire co-firing process. Thus, to
66 accurately predict the movement of straw particles in combustion chambers, it is imperative to
67 comprehensively consider other significant forces and torques in the CFD simulations ¹¹.

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Fig. 1 A straw based biomass shredding and conveying system.

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To date, a range of theoretical, experimental, and applied studies have successfully predicted the motion of non-spherical particles, primarily focusing on the deposition of small and non-reactive particles in a two-phase flow^{12,13}. However, no universal model is available for effectively addressing the impact of non-spherical straw biomass particles on the motion and combustion of direct co-firing in coal-fired boilers. Numerous researchers, such as Bhuiyan and Naser¹⁴, typically approximate biomass particles used in co-firing as spheres of equivalent volume, modifying only the drag coefficient correlations of traditional models. However, relatively few studies have focused specifically on the influence of irregularly shaped, large biomass particle trajectories in dilute-phase flows on co-firing performance. In our previous work⁹, a closed model was successfully developed and introduced for tracking large non-spherical particles, which simultaneously addressed the translation and rotation coupling motions of the particles. This model considers factors such as the aerodynamic drag lift, pitching and yawing moments, and the counter-rotation torque. Other studies, such as that carried out by Bonefacic et al.¹⁵, focused on cylindrical biomass particles in small-scale gasification fluidised bed reactors, considering the drag, lift, gravity, and pressure gradient forces of non-spherical particles; however, their rotation was overlooked. Furthermore, Zastawny¹⁶ and

87 Njobuenwu¹⁷ emphasised the significance of the particle shape in terms of the different aerodynamic
88 forces and torques, suggesting the applicability of this model for tracking various non-spherical
89 particles under turbulent conditions. Guo et al.¹⁸ presented a spheroid model that solves both
90 translational and rotational motion, demonstrating its impact in simulations of pulverized biomass jet
91 flows compared to conventional spherical particle models. However, the spheroid model did not
92 account for lift force. Although the current model partially reproduces experimental tests, such as the
93 settling of cylindrical polyvinyl chloride particles in a water tank, the uncertainties relating to the
94 aerodynamic coefficients of non-spherical cylindrical biomass particles under different particle and
95 flow conditions necessitate further examination and validation in the context of biomass suspended
96 combustion modelling¹⁹.

97 With the rapid development of computer technology, significant research has been conducted in
98 the field of particle-resolved direct numerical simulations (PR-DNS)²⁰, targeting various particle and
99 flow conditions⁶. In particular, research into aerodynamic parameters, such as the drag, lift, and
100 torque characteristics of non-spherical particles has garnered increasing attention²¹. In this context,
101 Schneiders et al.²² confirmed the requirement to accurately simulate the coupled translation and
102 rotation of non-spherical particles within a Lagrangian framework. This was achieved via
103 particle-resolved direct numerical simulations, wherein the crucial aerodynamic coefficients,
104 including the drag, lift, and torque, were explicitly defined as follows²³:

$$105 \quad C_D = \frac{|\overline{F_D}|}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_f A^* |\overline{u_f} - \overline{u_p}|^2}, C_L = \frac{|\overline{F_L}|}{\frac{1}{2}\rho_f A^* |\overline{u_f} - \overline{u_p}|^2}, C_T = \frac{|\overline{T}|}{\frac{1}{4}D_{eq}\rho_f A^* |\overline{u_f} - \overline{u_p}|^2} \quad (1)$$

106 where ρ_f is the fluid density, D_{eq} is the diameter of the spherical equivalent volume, $\overline{u_f}$ and
107 $\overline{u_p}$ is the flow and particles velocity, and $A^* = \pi D_{eq}^2 / 4$ is the cross-sectional area of a non-spherical
108 cylindrical particle. $\overline{F_D}$, $\overline{F_L}$, \overline{T} is the drag, lift, and torque, C_D , C_L , C_T is the corresponding

109 aerodynamic coefficients.

110 Recently, particle-resolved direct numerical simulations have been conducted for different
111 Reynolds numbers (Re), particle aspect ratios (AR), and incident angles (θ) to derive more precise
112 aerodynamic parameter relationships for non-spherical particles²⁴⁻²⁷. Based on these simulation
113 results, more general and precise correlations have been derived for the drag, lift, and torque
114 coefficients of representative non-spherical cylindrical particles, as reviewed in the literature²⁸⁻³⁶ and
115 summarised in Table 1.

116 Table 1 Correlation between cylindrical drag, lift and torque coefficients³⁷.

Reference	Applicability	Correlation
Hoerner ³⁸	Cylinders	$\frac{C_L}{C_D} = \sin^2 \theta \cos \theta $
Ganser ³⁰	Cylinders $10^{-4} < Re < 5 \times 10^5$	$C_D = \frac{24}{Re K_1 K_2} \left[1 + 0.1118 (Re K_1 K_2)^{0.6567} \right] + \frac{0.4305}{1 + 3305 / (Re K_1 K_2)}$
Clift et al. ²³	Long cylinders $40 < Re < 400$	$C_D = \frac{9.689}{Re^{0.78}} (1 + 0.0838 Re^{0.82})$
Hölzer and Sommerfeld ³⁹	Arbitrary shaped particles	$C_D = \frac{8}{Re} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varphi_{\perp}}} + \frac{16}{Re} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\varphi}} + \frac{3}{Re} \frac{1}{\varphi^{3/4}} + 0.4210^{0.4(-\log \varphi)^{0.2}} \frac{1}{\varphi_{\perp}}$
Vakil and Green ³⁵	Cylinders (2D) $2 \leq AR \leq 20$ $1 \leq Re \leq 40$	$C_D / C_{D,\perp} = (\beta_1 \ln(Re) + \beta_2) \cos(2\theta) + (\beta_3 \ln(Re) + \beta_4)$ $C_L = \left(\frac{\delta_1}{Re} + \delta_2 \right) \sin(2\theta) + (\delta_3 \ln(Re) + \delta_4) \sin(4\theta)$
Cao and Tafti ²⁶	Cylinders $AR = 1/4$ $10 \leq Re \leq 300$ $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$	$C_{D,\theta} = C_{D,\theta=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\theta=90^\circ} - C_{D,\theta=0^\circ}) \sin^2 \theta + 0.1280 Re^{0.2171} \sin \theta \cos \theta$ $C_{D,\theta=0^\circ} = \frac{24.335}{Re} (1 + 0.2129 Re^{0.6040})$ $C_{D,\theta=90^\circ} = \frac{24.2971}{Re^{0.5795}} + \frac{0.021}{Re^{-0.6799}}$ $C_{L,\theta} = \left(1.688 + \frac{6.617}{Re^{1.063}} + \frac{15.06}{Re} \right) (\sin \theta)^{0.8222} (\cos \theta)^{0.9796}$ $C_{T,\theta} = \left(19.28 + \frac{15.93}{Re^{0.02476}} \right) (\sin \theta)^{0.8929} (\cos \theta)^{0.9769}$
Lote et al. ³¹	$AR = 0.2, 0.3, 0.4$ $AR = 0.5, 0.6$ $0.1 \leq Re \leq 300$	$C_{D,\theta} = C_{D,\theta=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\theta=90^\circ} - C_{D,\theta=0^\circ}) \sin^2 \theta + 0.128 Re^{0.2171} \sin \theta \cos \theta$ $C_{L,\theta} = \left(b_1 + \frac{b_2}{Re} + \frac{b_3}{Re^{b_4}} + \frac{b_5}{Re^{b_6}} \right) (\sin \theta)^{(b_7 + b_8 Re^{b_9} + b_{10} Re^{b_{11}})} (\cos \theta)^{(b_{12} + b_{13} Re^{b_{14}} + b_{15} Re^{b_{16}})}$ $C_{T,\theta} = \left(c_1 + \frac{c_2}{Re} + \frac{c_3}{Re^{c_4}} + \frac{c_5}{Re^{c_6}} \right) (\sin \theta)^{(1+c_7 Re^{c_8})} (\cos \theta)^{(1+c_9 Re^{c_{10}})}$

117 However, the existing models are not fully applicable to real biomass combustion scenarios and
118 mainly lack a unified correlation formula that can cover cylindrical particles with a variety of aspect
119 ratios, a wider range of Reynolds numbers, and arbitrary incidence angles. our previous research
120 using OpenFOAM for direct numerical simulations was used to establish a new model for the drag,
121 lift and torque coefficients of cylindrical biomass particles and to validate its rationality and
122 applicability⁴⁰. It should also be noted that, as previously reported, the volatile content and fuel
123 reaction characteristics of biomass combustion are different from those of coal powder, and
124 non-spherical particles have different surface areas and average oxygen mass fluxes than spherical
125 particles⁴¹, thus requiring further refinement of biomass combustion models.

126 This study therefore aims to reliably simulate the movement and transformation of large
127 non-spherical straw biomass particles inside furnaces to enhance our understanding of biomass
128 combustion, and assist their optimisation. Initially, a closed model is introduced for tracking
129 cylindrical biomass particles in dilute multiphase flows, and the key issues associated with this new
130 motion model are considered to ensure its correct application in determining the drag, lift, and torque
131 coefficients⁴⁰. Subsequently, numerical simulations are carried out for straw/natural gas co-firing,
132 and the obtained results are compared with existing models to further assess the movement and
133 combustion of biomass particles in the new motion model.

134 **2 Theory and Methods**

135 **2.1 Aerodynamic modelling of novel cylindrical biomass particles**

136 Based on the existing particle-motion modeling framework in non-uniform flows proposed by
137 Yin et al.⁹, this study primarily addresses uncertainties in the calculations of drag coefficient, lift
138 coefficient, and pitching torque. The latter, pitching torque, is particularly sensitive to the distance
139 between the center of pressure and the centroid of non-spherical particles.

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141 To address this issue, a versatile model designed to accurately track the motion of
142 non-spherical cylindrical biomass particles under sparse multiphase flow conditions is proposed,
143 with the aim of resolving the coupling of particle translation and rotation. The key improvement of
144 this new model lies in the utilisation of more general and precise correlations for the drag, lift, and
145 pitching moment coefficients. These correlations were derived from our previous study on fully
146 resolved direct numerical simulations encompassing a wide range of cylindrical particle Reynolds
147 numbers, aspect ratios, and incident angles⁴⁰.

148 2.1.1 Coordinate systems and basic equations of motion

149 It is well known that the tracking of cylindrical particles involves coupled translation and
150 rotational motions, which must typically be described in different coordinate systems. As illustrated
151 in Fig. 2, the translational motion is considered in the inertial coordinate system, whereas the
152 rotational motion is described in the particle coordinate system.

153

154 Fig. 2 Inertial coordinate $\bar{X} = [x, y, z]$, particle coordinate $\bar{X}' = [x', y', z']$, and Euler angles (θ, ϕ, ψ)

155 In the particle coordinate system, to avoid singularities when determining the Euler angle rates,
156 quaternions⁴² are introduced to describe the orientations $\varepsilon = [\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2, \varepsilon_3, \eta]^T$, $\omega' = A\omega$, and
157 $T' = AT$ that are obtained from the coordinates in the inertial coordinate system through an
158 orthogonal transformation matrix A ¹³. The elements of the transformation matrix represent the
159 directional cosines of the particle axes in the inertial coordinate system, as represented in Equation
160 (2):

$$161 \quad A = \begin{bmatrix} 1 - 2(\varepsilon_2^2 + \varepsilon_3^2) & 2(\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_2 + \varepsilon_3\eta) & 2(\varepsilon_1\varepsilon_3 - \varepsilon_2\eta) \\ 2(\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_1 - \varepsilon_3\eta) & 1 - 2(\varepsilon_3^2 + \varepsilon_1^2) & 2(\varepsilon_2\varepsilon_3 + \varepsilon_1\eta) \\ 2(\varepsilon_3\varepsilon_1 + \varepsilon_2\eta) & 2(\varepsilon_3\varepsilon_2 - \varepsilon_1\eta) & 1 - 2(\varepsilon_1^2 + \varepsilon_2^2) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

162 The quaternions are computed using Euler angles (θ, ϕ, ψ) and are continuously updated over time.
163 They must be normalised at each time step $|\varepsilon| = 1$ to prevent the accumulation of numerical errors
164 (see Equations (3) and (4))⁴².

$$165 \quad \begin{cases} \varepsilon_1 = \cos \frac{\phi - \psi}{2} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ \varepsilon_2 = \sin \frac{\phi - \psi}{2} \sin \frac{\theta}{2} \\ \varepsilon_3 = \sin \frac{\phi + \psi}{2} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \\ \eta = \cos \frac{\phi + \psi}{2} \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$166 \quad \begin{bmatrix} d\varepsilon_1 / dt \\ d\varepsilon_2 / dt \\ d\varepsilon_3 / dt \\ d\eta / dt \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} \eta w'_x - \varepsilon_3 w'_y + \varepsilon_2 w'_z \\ \varepsilon_3 w'_x + \eta w'_y - \varepsilon_1 w'_z \\ -\varepsilon_2 w'_x + \varepsilon_1 w'_y + \eta w'_z \\ -\varepsilon_1 w'_x - \varepsilon_2 w'_y - \varepsilon_3 w'_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

167 For the translational motion, the non-spherical particle motion equation established by Callil
168 and Cohen⁴³ for arbitrary turbulence was adopted. In their study on the resolution of wall
169 deposition issues for small ellipsoidal particles in turbulent flows, Fan and Ahmadi¹³ found that in
170 the inertial coordinate system, the linear motion of the particles satisfies Newton's second law (see
171 Equations (5) and (6)). In contrast, the rotational motion is considered in the particle coordinate

172 system and is aligned with the principal axes of inertia (see Equations (7)).

173
$$\frac{d\vec{r}}{dt} = \vec{u}_p \quad (5)$$

174
$$m_p \frac{d\vec{u}_p}{dt} = \vec{F} \quad (6)$$

175
$$I' \frac{d\omega'}{dt} + \omega' \times (I' \omega') = T' \quad (7)$$

176 In these equations, r is the position of the particle centre of mass, m_p , \vec{u}_p and \vec{F} are the
177 mass, velocity, and net aerodynamic force acting on the particle, respectively, and I' , ω' , T' are
178 the diagonal tensors of inertia. The angular velocity of a non-spherical particle defined in the
179 particle coordinate system results from aerodynamic torque acting about the particle's center of
180 pressure (rather than its center of mass).

181 2.1.2 Cylinder motion control equations

182 Currently, the standard Lagrangian point mass model is commonly employed to simulate
183 particle phase dynamics. In non-uniform flow fields, the Maxey-Riley equation¹³ is often used to
184 address particle motion. The ultimate objective of this study was to track cylindrical biomass
185 particles within a combustion chamber. In contrast to spherical particles, gravitational effects are
186 considered in addition to the drag (\overline{F}_D), lift (\overline{F}_L), virtual mass force (\overline{F}_{VM}), virtual mass force
187 (\overline{F}_{VM}), and forces resulting from pressure gradients in the airflow (\overline{F}_{PG}). Consequently, the
188 governing equation for the linear motion evolution of particles is represented by Equation (8):

189
$$\overline{F}_D + \overline{F}_L + \overline{F}_{VM} + \overline{F}_{PG} + (\rho_p - \rho_f)V_p \vec{g} = m_p \frac{d\vec{u}_p}{dt} = \vec{F} \quad (8)$$

190 In the new cylindrical particle motion model, neglecting the Faxen correction term, Basset
191 history term, thermophoretic force, Brownian force, and Saffman lift force is considered acceptable
192 for the particle force balance under gas-solid dilute-phase flow conditions⁹. The virtual mass
193 gradient force, pressure gradient force, and gravity were therefore calculated according to the

194 standard definitions, as presented in Equations (9) and (10):

195
$$\overline{F_{VM}} = \frac{1}{2} \rho_f V_p \frac{d(\overline{u_f} - \overline{u_p})}{dt} \quad (9)$$

196
$$\overline{F_{PG}} = \rho_f V_p \frac{D\overline{u_f}}{Dt} \quad (10)$$

197 Where $\overline{u_p}$, m_p , V_p and ρ_p are the undisturbed velocity, mass, volume, and density of the
198 particle, respectively, while $\overline{u_f}$, ρ_f and \overline{g} represent the undisturbed velocity, density, and
199 gravitational acceleration of the airflow, respectively. The drag ($\overline{F_D}$) and lift ($\overline{F_L}$) are determined
200 from the angles of the particles ¹².

201 Furthermore, the rotational motion is relative to the three-particle centroid axes due to the
202 torque (\overline{T}) exerted by the flow on the particle centroid, which causes the particle to rotate about its
203 centroidal principal axis ⁴⁴. Thus, according to Equation (11):

204
$$\begin{cases} I_{x'} \frac{d\omega_{x'}}{dt} - \omega_{y'} \omega_{z'} (I_{y'} - I_{z'}) = T_{x'} \\ I_{y'} \frac{d\omega_{y'}}{dt} - \omega_{z'} \omega_{x'} (I_{z'} - I_{x'}) = T_{y'} \\ I_{z'} \frac{d\omega_{z'}}{dt} - \omega_{x'} \omega_{y'} (I_{x'} - I_{y'}) = T_{z'} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

205 Where $[\omega_{x'}, \omega_{y'}, \omega_{z'}]$, $[I_{x'}, I_{y'}, I_{z'}]$ and $[T_{x'}, T_{y'}, T_{z'}]$ are the particle angular velocity, the moment
206 of inertia, and the torque components, respectively, along the three centroid axes. The moment of
207 inertia of cylindrical particles can be expressed as $I_{x'} = I_{y'} = \frac{1}{4} m_p a^2 + \frac{1}{3} m_p c^2$ or $I_{z'} = \frac{1}{2} m_p b^2$,
208 where the aspect ratio ($AR = 2c/2a$) is defined as the ratio of the long semi-axis (c) to the short
209 semi-axis (a). The b is the short semi-axis of the particle equal to a .

210 2.1.3 A Novel cylinder Lagrange model

211 Recently, Mortensen et al. ⁴⁵, Marchioli et al. ⁴⁶, and Siewert et al. ⁴⁷ established Lagrangian
212 models using ellipsoids. However, in order to take into account the relevance of cylindrical particles,
213 it is necessary to recalibrate their aerodynamic equations and to extend their range of application.

214 Under creeping flow conditions, the drag and lift are defined by the drag tensor; but, when the
215 Reynolds number is $Re > 0$, the correlation between the drag and lift must be described separately²¹.
216 as outlined in Equations (12) and (13):

$$217 \quad \overline{F}_D = \frac{1}{2} C_D \rho_f A_p \left| \overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p \right| (\overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p) \quad (12)$$

$$218 \quad \overline{F}_L = \frac{1}{2} C_L \rho_f A_p \text{sign}(\overline{z}' \cdot (\overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p)) \left[\overline{z}' \times (\overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p) \right] \times (\overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p) \quad (13)$$

219 Where \overline{z}' is the long axis direction of the particle, A_p and D_{eq} are the equivalent sphere
220 cross-sectional area and diameter of the cylindrical particles, with $A_p = \pi D_{eq}^2 / 4$. The relative
221 velocity vector $\overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p$ between the fluid and the particles, and the angle change in the long-axis
222 \overline{z}' of the particle are referred to as the orientation angles α . Where in $\text{sign}(\cos\alpha) = 1$ if
223 $\cos\alpha > 0$; $\text{sign}(\cos\alpha) = -1$ otherwise.

224 For spherical particles, orientation effects are typically neglected in Lagrangian modeling
225 approaches, as previous studies have demonstrated that their influence on overall particle dynamics is
226 minor⁴⁸. However, for non-spherical particles, the importance of torque cannot be overlooked ($Re >$
227 0). With this in mind, Jeffery⁴⁹ derived the fluid dynamic torque imparted on ellipsoids in creeping
228 shear flows. The first term on the right-hand side of Equation (14) represents the torque caused by the
229 relative rotation between the particles and the surrounding local fluid flow, while the second term
230 corresponds to the torque caused by flow separation damping (which does not involve particle
231 translation or rotation), and the third term is the main contribution to the torque, i.e., the pitch torque
232 caused by the airflow on the particle^{21,22}. The direction of torque \overline{d}_T and drag \overline{d}_D is given by
233 Equations (15)-(16).

$$234 \quad \overline{T} = \mu \overline{\mathbf{K}}_w \cdot (\overline{\omega}_f - \overline{\omega}_p) + \mu \overline{\mathbf{K}}_s \cdot \overline{\mathcal{S}}_f + A \left(\frac{1}{2} C_T \rho_f \frac{A_p D_{eq}}{2} \left| \overline{u}_f - \overline{u}_p \right|^2 \overline{d}_T \right) \quad (14)$$

$$235 \quad \overline{d}_T = \frac{\overline{z}' \times \overline{d}_D \left(-\text{sgn}(\overline{z}' \cdot \overline{d}_D) \right)}{\left| \overline{z}' \times \overline{d}_D \left(-\text{sgn}(\overline{z}' \cdot \overline{d}_D) \right) \right|} \quad (15)$$

$$236 \quad \overline{d_D} = \frac{(\overline{u_f} - \overline{u_p})}{|\overline{u_f} - \overline{u_p}|} \quad (16)$$

237 These (\overline{T}) are related to the rate of stress change in the particle position $(\overline{S_f})$ and the fluid
238 angular velocity $(\overline{\omega_f})$ ²¹, as defined by Equations (17) and (18):

$$239 \quad \overline{S_f} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y'} + \frac{\partial u_{y'}}{\partial z'}, \frac{\partial u_{x'}}{\partial z'} + \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x'}, \frac{\partial u_{y'}}{\partial x'} + \frac{\partial u_{x'}}{\partial y'} \right)^T \quad (17)$$

$$240 \quad \overline{\omega_f} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial u_z}{\partial y'} - \frac{\partial u_{y'}}{\partial z'}, \frac{\partial u_{x'}}{\partial z'} - \frac{\partial u_z}{\partial x'}, \frac{\partial u_{y'}}{\partial x'} - \frac{\partial u_{x'}}{\partial y'} \right)^T \quad (18)$$

241 The diagonal drag tensor $(\overline{K_w}$ and $\overline{K_s})$ relative to the angular velocity and the strain rate of a
242 particle can be expressed as presented in Equations (19) and (20), respectively:

$$243 \quad \overline{K_w} = \frac{16}{3} \pi A R a^3 \begin{pmatrix} \frac{a^2 + b^2}{a^2 \alpha_0 + b^2 \gamma_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{a^2 + b^2}{a^2 \alpha_0 + b^2 \gamma_0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{\alpha_0} \end{pmatrix} \quad (19)$$

$$245 \quad \overline{K_s} = \frac{16}{3} \pi A R a^3 \begin{pmatrix} \frac{a^2 - b^2}{a^2 \alpha_0 + b \gamma_0} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{c^2 - a^2}{a^2 \alpha_0 + b^2 \gamma_0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (20)$$

246 The analytical expression for the shape parameters of cylindrical (κ , α_0 and γ_0) particles is
247 shown in Equations (21)-(23) below, where $AR > 1$. In this context, Brenner and Cox^{50,51} demonstrated
248 that any diagonal tensor of the particle shape can be constructed using shape parameters.

$$249 \quad \kappa = \log \left(\frac{AR - \sqrt{AR^2 - 1}}{AR + \sqrt{AR^2 - 1}} \right) \quad (21)$$

$$250 \quad \alpha_0 = \frac{AR^2}{AR^2 - 1} + \frac{AR}{2(AR^2 - 1)^{3/2}} \kappa \quad (22)$$

$$251 \quad \gamma_0 = -\frac{2}{AR^2 - 1} - \frac{AR}{(AR^2 - 1)^{3/2}} \kappa \quad (23)$$

252 **2.1.4 Incorporation cylindrical particle correlation force coefficient model**

253 The current calculation of drag coefficients within the Lagrangian modeling framework suffers
254 from limited generality, particularly as variations in particle geometry further exacerbate the
255 discrepancies. Based on our previous modeling of cylindrical straw biomass particles co-fired in
256 coal-fired boilers, and the force coefficient correlations obtained through direct numerical
257 simulations using OpenFOAM⁵², more general and accurate correlations have been developed for
258 cylinders with $AR \leq 18$, $Re \leq 2000$, and incidence angles $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 90^\circ$ ³⁷. These correlations are
259 complete and readily implementable within the current Lagrangian modeling framework²¹.

260 Drag and lift coefficient models based on the analytical expressions reported by Happel and
261 Brenner under a Stokes flow⁵³ were established to describe the drag and lift properties of
262 cylindrical biomass particles⁴⁰. The new model results showed a good agreement with the direct
263 numerical simulation results, with root mean square errors of 8.8×10^{-2} and 2.4×10^{-2} , along with
264 average relative errors of 5.8 and 3.5%, and median relative errors of 4.27 and 4.97%, respectively,
265 as defined by Equations (24)-(31):

$$266 \quad C_{D,\theta} = C_{D,\theta=0^\circ} + (C_{D,\theta=90^\circ} - C_{D,\theta=0^\circ}) \sin^2 \theta \quad (24)$$

$$267 \quad C_{D,\theta=0^\circ/90^\circ} = \left(\frac{a_1}{Re} + \frac{a_2}{Re^{a_3}} \right) e^{-Re^{a_4}} + a_5 (1 - e^{-Re^{a_4}}) \quad (25)$$

$$268 \quad a_{1,\theta=0^\circ} = \frac{24}{AR^{1/3}} \left[-\frac{2AR}{AR^2 - 1} + \frac{2AR^2 - 1}{(AR^2 - 1)^{3/2}} \ln \left(\frac{AR + \sqrt{AR^2 - 1}}{AR - \sqrt{AR^2 - 1}} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (26)$$

$$269 \quad a_{1,\theta=90^\circ} = \frac{24}{AR^{1/3}} \left[\frac{AR}{AR^2 - 1} + \frac{2AR^2 - 3}{(AR^2 - 1)^{3/2}} \ln \left(AR + \sqrt{AR^2 - 1} \right) \right]^{-1} \quad (27)$$

$$270 \quad C_{L,\theta} = C_{L,mag} \sin \psi_\theta \cos \psi_\theta \quad (28)$$

$$271 \quad C_{L,mag} = \left(\frac{b_1}{Re} + \frac{b_2}{Re^{b_3}} + b_4 \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + e^{-0.01(Re-600)}} \right) + \frac{1}{1 + e^{-0.01(Re-600)}} b_5 \quad (29)$$

$$272 \quad \psi_{\theta} = 1.57 \left(\frac{\theta}{1.57} \right)^{f_{L,shift}} \quad (30)$$

$$273 \quad f_{L,shift} = 1 + S_1 (\ln AR) (\ln Re)^{S_2} \quad (31)$$

274 The torque coefficient depends on the nonlinear drag and lift of the particles, with a trend
275 similar to that of the lift coefficient. The root mean square error and average relative error between
276 the torque coefficient model and numerical simulation results were determined to be 4.7×10^{-3} and
277 8.17%, respectively, with a median relative error of 8.36%, as defined by Equations (32)-(35):

$$278 \quad C_{T,\theta} = C_{T,mag} \sin \psi_{\theta} \cos \psi_{\theta} \quad (32)$$

$$279 \quad C_{T,mag} = \left(\frac{c_1}{Re^{c_2}} + c_3 \right) \quad (33)$$

$$280 \quad \psi_{\theta} = 1.57 \left(\frac{\theta}{1.57} \right)^{f_{T,shift}} \quad (34)$$

$$281 \quad f_{T,shift} = 1 - \left(T_1 - \frac{T_2}{T_3 + e^{-(AR-T_4)}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{1}{1 + e^{f_1(Re-f_2)}} \right) \quad (35)$$

282 Detailed descriptions of the relevant parameters of these models are provided in our previous
283 studies^{37,40}. It should be noted that a certain transformation relationship exists between the incident
284 angles θ of the drag, lift, and torque coefficients and the orientation angles α within the
285 Lagrange model framework, which satisfies $\theta = \alpha$ if $\alpha \leq \pi / 2$; $\theta = \pi - \alpha$ otherwise.

286 2.1.5 Computational process

287 Using the complete model described above, the translational and rotational motions of biomass
288 particles during the suspension combustion process are solved through a User-Defined Function
289 (UDF) implementation. All governing equations are expressed in dimensionless form. The coupling
290 algorithmic strategy employed in the computation is illustrated in Fig. 3. Notably, this approach
291 differs significantly from the default spherical particle treatment in FLUENT 2022R1, particularly
292 in the case of cylindrical biomass particles, as illustrated in Fig. 4.

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Fig. 3 Algorithmic illustration of the cylindrical particle motion model.

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Fig. 4 Coupling approach (FLUENT-UDF).

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2.2 Burner meshing and biomass particle sizing in case application studies

299 The Fig. 5 illustrates the structure of the natural gas/biomass co-fired burner model, wherein
300 the biomass enters the furnace through a central duct along with primary air (PA), while another
301 external annular duct supplies natural gas (NG) and secondary air separately (SA). Based on the
302 actual structure and dimensions of the burner, it was meticulously modelled using the ICEM
303 geometric modelling software. Owing to the complex burner structure, zoning was performed using
304 structured grids prior to grid division. Grids aligned with the fluid flow direction were employed at
305 the burner outlet, and localised grid refinement was employed to accurately simulate the large
306 physical quantity gradients in this area. Table 2 lists the dimensions and shapes of the cylindrical
307 biomass particles after their preparation for direct co-firing, a process that has been successfully
308 applied in the suspension combustion of straw/natural gas at the Funen Power Plant ⁵⁴. This
309 involved individual classification and statistical analysis of the particle size distributions of the
310 crushed biomass samples, in addition to calculation of the particle sphericities and equivalent
311 diameters. At the same time, the industrial and elemental analyses of the co-firing biomass raw
312 materials considered in this study, along with the burner operating conditions, are presented in Table
313 3.

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Fig. 5 Geometry and structure of the natural gas/biomass co-fired burner:

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(a) mesh and inlet layout; (b) internal flow arrangement and burner dimensions.

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Table 2 Size distributions of co-firing the straw particles after crushing

Particle sets [NO.]	Long axis [mm]	Short axis [mm]	Mass fraction [wt%]	Equivalent volume diameter, D_{eq} [mm]	Sphericity factor ϕ
Straw particles with nodes (solid pieces); density of 250 kg/m ³					
0	130.3	4.8	0.3784	16.5135	0.4281
1	90.0	4.1	0.5176	13.1412	0.4576
2	70.0	4.0	1.1923	13.2372	0.5153
3	50.0	3.9	2.7399	12.3311	0.5793
4	32.5	3.7	3.2728	9.6599	0.6263
5	18.5	3.7	2.4512	7.2425	0.6966
6	9.0	3.8	0.369	5.7983	0.8117
Straw particles with heads (solid pieces, whisklike); density of 139 kg/m ³					
7	100.1	2.5	0.3562	9.7904	0.3783
8	70.0	2.5	0.2938	8.6901	0.424
9	50.0	2.5	0.8011	7.7681	0.471
10	32.5	2.5	1.0864	6.7209	0.5366
11	20.0	2.5	0.9617	5.7236	0.6155
12	10.5	2.5	0.6824	4.6173	0.7258
13	60.0	2.0	1.5588	5.6836	0.2648
14	45.0	1.95	4.0015	5.1128	0.2916
15	30.0	1.73	19.9105	4.2584	0.3396
16	20.0	1.49	22.9046	3.499	0.3961
17	15.0	1.42	16.2812	3.1155	0.4351
18	8.0	0.53	11.6111	1.051	0.4374
19	4.0	0.33	4.2174	0.6772	0.5754
20	2.0	0.22	2.3829	0.4481	0.6712
21	1.0	0.1	2.0256	0.1651	0.7788

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332

Table 3 Proximate, ultimate, and simulation parameters of co-firing straw biomass

Straw	Proximate analysis (wt%)				Ultimate analysis (wt%)				$Q_{net,ar}$ (MJ/kg)	
	M_{ar}	V_{ar}	FC_{ar}	A_{ar}	C_{daf}	H_{daf}	O_{daf}	N_{daf}		S_{daf}
	14	67.1	15.1	3.8	47.5	5.9	45.75	0.7	0.15	14.9
Gas	Gas composition (wt%)						$Q_{net,ar}$ (MJ/kg)			
	CH_4	C_2H_6	C_3H_8	C_4H_{10}	CO_2					
	81.23	81.23	4.55	4.55	1.37		48.55			
Mass flow (kg/s)	Straw		Gas		First air		Secondary air			
	1.46		0.406		1.28		14.3			

333

334 2.3 Model validation and working condition setting

335 To validate the current motion model framework, the motion of cylindrical polyvinyl chloride
336 (PVC) particles was evaluated in a water tank. Taking a cylindrical PVC particle (diameter 5.41 mm,
337 length 50 mm) released from a static state in the tank (ρ_p / ρ_f is 1.366) as an example, the
338 predicted motion pattern of the model was compared with the experimental measurements. The
339 predicted particle motion trajectory from our numerical model was directly compared with the
340 experimental observations, as illustrated clearly in Fig. 6(a)-(b). The results show very good
341 agreement between numerical predictions and experimental measurements of particle drop direction
342 displacement and fluid-particle incidence angle, with an overall error of less than 5%. This close
343 agreement strongly demonstrates the feasibility and accuracy of our proposed motion modelling
344 framework. Furthermore, the final flow field in the flume, as shown in Fig. 6(c), confirms the
345 proper coupling between the fluid phase and the particle dynamics during the settling process. This
346 detailed validation further demonstrates the ability of the present model to accurately capture the
347 particle-fluid interactions.

349 Fig. 6 Validation of the current model based on the settling of a cylindrical PVC particle in a water tank. (a) Phase
350 coupling, (b) Particle translation, and (c) Particle rotation.

351 The commercial CFD software FLUENT 2022R1 is an effective tool for simulating coal

352 powder combustion in power plants¹⁵. FLUENT incorporates the various sub-models that are
353 necessary for coal combustion, including turbulence, heat transfer, and combustion. Although
354 biomass combustion involves many similar processes, differences in the biomass and coal
355 characteristics result in different combustion. Previous FLUENT numerical simulations primarily
356 focused on combustion in coal powder burners, simplifying the shapes and sizes of the biomass
357 particles, often assuming them to be spherical, and correcting non-spherical particles using shape
358 factors. However, the large particle sizes and significant non-sphericity lead to different trajectories
359 and combustion modes, which are critical factors that affect the numerical simulation results. Thus,
360 considering the CFD numerical simulation calculation case listed in Table 4, the computational
361 results of the coupled and uncoupled model are discussed. More specifically, simulations were
362 conducted for cases 1-4. The standard k- ϵ turbulence model (Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
363 RANS approach) was employed due to its computational efficiency, given the large simulation
364 domain (10 m) and the requirement to track numerous particles. This choice enables practical
365 comparison among different particle motion models. Although advanced models (e.g., Large Eddy
366 Simulation LES) could provide more flow details, their high computational cost was considered
367 unsuitable for the current study. So the turbulent gas-phase flow was simulated using the realisable
368 k- ϵ two-equation model, with the Eddy dissipation model (EDM) being employed to simulate
369 turbulent gas-phase combustion during component transport. During combustion, most of the heat
370 was transferred via radiative heat transfer, as evaluated using the discrete ordinate (DO) method⁵⁵.
371 In addition, the soot emission rate was calculated using the grey-weighted spectral gas model
372 (WSGGM)⁵⁶. In terms of the material property parameters, the basic combustion reactions were
373 customised based on the assumed complex hydrocarbon formula $C_xH_yO_zS_mN_n$, while the release
374 of volatiles was predicted using a single-rate kinetic devolatilisation model⁵⁷. The precursor factor

375 was set at $1.0 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and the activation energy was $7.4 \times 10^7 \text{ J/mol}$. Combustion of the biomass
376 volatiles and char was modelled using a diffusion-limited model, wherein processes occurring in
377 both the gas phase and at the solid–gas interface were considered. FLUENT incorporated a
378 comprehensive model based on the Lagrangian particle discrete-phase of stochastic orbital model
379 combustion method.

380 Table 4 Computational cases for implementation of the cylindrical particle model

Case	Discrete term model	Combustion model
1	All particles simplified as equivalent volume spheres; only particle translation solved, using the spherical drag law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Realizable k-ε model for turbulence • Discrete model for thermal radiation: domain-based WSGGM for gaseous radiative properties
2	All particles simplified as equivalent volume spheres; only particle translation solved, using the non-spherical drag law	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Radiative heat transfer using the discrete ordinate method (DO)
3	UDF: All particles modelled as cylindrical ; the new, closed model used: solving both particle translation and rotation, incorporating drag/lift/torque coefficients derived from particle-resolved DNS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two-step global combustion mechanism for gas combustion with CO as the intermediate product Finite rate/eddy dissipation for turbulence-chemistry interaction • Same particle surface area used in laws for particle-gas heat and mass exchange • Single-rate model for biomass devolatilization
4	UDF: All particles modelled as cylindrical ; the new, closed model used: solving both particle translation and rotation, incorporating drag/lift/torque coefficients derived from particle-resolved DNS	UDF: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-spherical cylindrical particle surface area used in laws for particle-gas heat and mass exchange • Diffusion-limited char burning model due to large particle size, in which the non-spherical cylindrical enhancement factor $\varphi_{en} = (0.3\varphi + 0.7)/\varphi$ is used

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386 In case 1, the biomass particles were treated as equivolume spherical particles, considering
387 only drag. In case 2, the drag coefficient of the equivolume particles was corrected using a
388 sphericity factor between 0.2 and 0.8 (i.e., the ratio of the equivolume spherical surface area to the
389 actual surface area of the non-spherical particles). Case 3 was based on the newly developed closed
390 cylindrical biomass particles motion model for using UDF. In Case 4, a shape factor correction was
391 applied to the equivalent spherical cross-sectional area of the particle during heating and
392 Devolatilization through a UDF to account for the effects of particle morphology on
393 thermochemical conversion⁵⁴. Meanwhile, an enhancement factor was introduced to adjust the char
394 combustion process. Compared with Case 3, in which cylindrical particle motion was considered,
395 the model in Case 4 further incorporates the influence of specific surface area and oxygen diffusion
396 rate to the particle surface for non-spherical particles, offering a more comprehensive treatment of
397 the combustion behavior. These implementations build upon the findings of our previous research⁵⁴.
398 The SIMPLE algorithm was used to solve the pressure-velocity coupling of the discrete equation
399 sets for all cases by employing a first-order upwind scheme for all equations. Prior to conducting
400 the comparative numerical simulations, a grid-independence test was performed on the combustor
401 to ensure that the selected grid number (100,000) does not affect computational accuracy while
402 minimising computational cost. Three distinct grid resolutions (60,000, 100,000, and 150,000 cells)
403 were tested, and the velocity and temperature profiles along the combustor centreline were
404 compared. The outcomes of this investigation revealed that there were negligible differences (less
405 than 1%) between the 100,000 cell and 150,000 cell grids, thereby confirming that the 100,000 cell
406 grid provided grid-independent solutions with optimal computational efficiency.

407 **3 Results and Discussion**

408 **3.1 Temperature and component distributions**

409 The temperature distribution of the burner under four different cases operating conditions is
410 shown in Fig. 7 to Fig. 8 . Under all cases conditions, the natural gas undergoes rapid combustion
411 near the burner nozzle, forming a stable flame around the cold biomass. Firstly, whether the
412 biomass is modeled as equivalent volume spherical particles (case 1) or its drag coefficient is
413 corrected using a sphericity factor (case 2), the cold biomass particle jet extends along the burner
414 centerline for a considerable distance of approximately 3.5 meters. In contrast, under case 3, this
415 distance is reduced to only about 1.5 meter. This shortened distance reflects a reduced residence
416 time required for biomass particles to be heated and undergo devolatilisation. This is primarily
417 attributed to the advanced dynamic behavior considered in case 3, where the cylindrical shape of the
418 biomass is fully accounted for, including the effects of drag, lift, and torque. As a result, the flame
419 formed by volatile combustion remains nearly horizontal, in contrast to the noticeably
420 downward-curved flame observed in cases 1 and 2. The volatiles are released earlier and more
421 rapidly, thereby shortening the time needed for biomass heating and devolatilisation.

422 Furthermore, building upon case 3, the geometric characteristics of non-spherical biomass
423 particles are further refined in case 4 by incorporating shape factors and enhancement coefficients
424 to account for their influence on combustion. As a result, the heating rate of cylindrical biomass
425 particles in case 4 is faster than that in case 3, where the original equivalent volume spherical
426 particle combustion model is employed. Although existing literature suggests adjusting the natural
427 gas nozzle angle toward the centerline to reduce the ignition distance of the biomass flame and
428 enhance the heating of the cold biomass stream⁵⁸, it overlooks the fact that real biomass, due to its
429 high volatile content and larger surface area, is more accurately represented by case 4. In this case,
430 the flame formed downstream of the burner is significantly higher than in the other cases,
431 promoting more complete combustion.

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Fig. 7 Temperature distribution in the co-firing burner.

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Fig. 8 Temperature distribution cloud for the combustor cross-section.

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Figures 9 and 10 illustrate the release of volatiles under different cases operating conditions, further validating the differential analysis of the volatiles presented in Figs. 7 and 8. In cases 3 and 4, considering the aerodynamics of the non-spherical particles, the release of volatiles occurred significantly earlier, accompanied by the substantial consumption of oxygen along the centreline of the burner, as evidenced by Fig. 11 to Fig. 12. This trend is particularly evident in case 4, which incorporates a combustion model accounting for the cylindrical shape of biomass particles. It is

442 consistent with our previous findings and effectively reproduces the combustion behavior induced by
443 the intrinsic characteristics of biomass⁹. Notably, the presence of a considerable amount of unreacted
444 volatiles in the burner indicates that the air distribution can be further optimised¹⁵. For low nitrogen
445 oxide (NO_x) burner designs, a lower oxygen concentration along the centreline is advantageous
446 because it reduces NO_x formation. However, for biomass burner designs, maintaining an adequate air
447 supply is crucial to prevent delayed biomass combustion, which positively affects the flame length
448 and the degree of biomass burnout. Nevertheless, excessive air supply can also delay the heating of
449 the cold biomass stream and the release of volatiles, primarily because the surplus air lowers the
450 temperature of the natural gas flame around the burner, resulting in effects similar to those caused by
451 insufficient air supply.

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Fig. 9 Distribution of volatiles in the co-firing burner.

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Fig. 10 Distribution of the volatile fraction in the burner cross-section.

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Fig. 11 Oxygen distribution in the co-firing burner

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Fig. 12 Oxygen distribution clouds in the burner cross-section.

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461 3.2 Biomass particle trajectory

462 For each case, a total of 1,980 biomass particle streams were tracked within the burner,
463 corresponding to 22 cylindrical shapes with different aspect ratios (injection types) multiplied by 90
464 injection positions. Figure 13 illustrates the variation in the biomass particle concentration under the
465 four different cases operating conditions. By observing the differences in the overall particle
466 trajectories, it was found that the aerodynamics of the non-spherical particles and the optimised
467 combustion model (Consider the specific surface area of cylindrical particles) were mainly
468 responsible for determining the trajectories. In cases 3 and 4, the biomass particles were
469 approximated as cylinders, considering various aspect ratios, Reynolds numbers, and the drag, lift,
470 and torque coefficient new models under different incident angles. All significant forces, including
471 the drag, lift, virtual mass force, pressure gradient force, and gravity, were considered, rendering the
472 aerodynamic motion of the biomass particles more consistent with reality. The inclusion of
473 non-spherical particle geometric features results in a faster biomass heating rate and earlier release

474 of volatile components in the numerical simulation compared to cases 1 and 2, which only consider
475 drag coefficient corrections based on equivalent volume spheres and sphericity factors. In case 4,
476 the combustion model was optimised based on case 3, leading to faster particle mass loss and a
477 greater decline in the particle concentration compared to those under the other cases operating
478 conditions. These factors were extensively discussed in a study by Bonefacic et al. ¹⁵, who
479 emphasised their importance throughout the combustion process.

480

481

Fig. 13 Particle concentrations in the co-firing burner.

482 To further compare the significance of the particle aerodynamics and optimised combustion,
483 representative biomass particles, including particle No.0 with the maximum aspect ratio, particle
484 No.16 with the highest mass fraction, and particle No.20 with smaller dimensions, were selected for
485 comparison (Table 2). All particles are injected from the PA nozzle, with all other initial conditions
486 held constant. Specifically, each particle is initially oriented at a 45° inclination relative to the flow
487 direction, with zero angular velocity. In Fig. 14 to 16, we compare the burnout fraction (including
488 both volatiles and char) along particle trajectories under varying particle densities. In the burner, the
489 initial mass fractions of volatiles and char for co-fired biomass particles are 78% and 17.5%,
490 respectively.

491 For particles No.16 and No. 20, clear differences were observed in the release of the volatile
492 components (density of 139 kg/m^3) and particle trajectories. Relative to cases 1 and 2, a greater
493 degree of bending toward the center and a longer particle residence time were observed in case 3.
494 This is consistent with the previous analysis and is attributed to the more precise aerodynamic
495 modeling of non-spherical biomass particles in case 3. Compared to Case 3, the combustion rate in
496 Case 4 (i.e., the rate of particle mass loss) is faster, primarily due to the combined effects of novel
497 aerodynamic and combustion optimization models. However, despite incorporating these
498 enhancements, the combustion performance of Particle No. 0 (density of 250 kg/m^3) remains
499 unsatisfactory, mainly due to its large size (length is 130 mm, diameter is 4 mm), which aligns with
500 incomplete combustion phenomena commonly observed in practical applications. This correlates
501 with a previous study by Lu ⁵⁹, where an increase in the biomass particle size generally led to a
502 reduced mass combustion ⁶⁰. Nevertheless, the overall trajectories of the particles are still superior
503 to the trajectories that take into account the drag coefficient corrections based only on the
504 equivalent volume spherical and spherical factor models.

Fig. 14 Tracking of particle No.0 in the co-firing burner (density of 250 kg/m^3).

Fig. 15 Tracking of particle No.16 in the co-firing burner (density of 139 kg/m³).

Fig. 16 Tracking of particle No.20 in the co-firing burner (density of 139 kg/m³).

512 Through a comparative analysis of the oxygen concentration, temperature, particle burnout,
513 and volatile release properties along the centreline of the burner (see Fig.17 to Fig.20), it was
514 observed that cases 3 and 4 outperformed the scenarios in which biomass was treated as point-like
515 spherical particles or when only spherical factor corrected drag coefficients were used.

516 In cases 3 and 4, no delayed combustion was observed after the biomass particles entered the
517 burner. The novel aerodynamic model effectively prevents the particles from rapidly falling to the
518 bottom of the burner. In contrast, cases 1 and 2 do not sufficiently account for additional
519 aerodynamic forces-such as lift, virtual mass force, pressure gradient force, and torque induced
520 rotational effects-which results in inadequate aerodynamic support for the relatively large size
521 biomass particles. Consequently, the particles tend to fall quickly to the burner bottom for
522 combustion, rather than exiting the furnace as biomass ash. Previously, Gera et al.⁶¹ emphasised the

523 significant impact of aerodynamics on the movement of large particles. In contrast, the novel model
524 incorporates all the key forces into the translational and rotational motion equations of the particles
525 (Equation 8). The drag, lift, and torque coefficients in this model are obtained from direct numerical
526 simulations of thousands of particle-resolved cases, covering a wide spectrum of flow and particle
527 conditions. These conditions are characterized by particle Reynolds number, aspect ratio, and
528 incident angles, ensuring high accuracy and broad applicability. As a result, the numerical
529 simulation results under the novel model align more closely with the real conditions observed
530 during co-firing in practical applications. Under the novel model, the numerical simulation results
531 more accurately reflect the real conditions observed during co-firing, such as the increased
532 residence time of biomass particles within the burner, as well as the earlier release of volatiles and a
533 significant improvement in burnout rate efficiency. Building upon this, case 4 further incorporates
534 the shape factor of cylindrical particles into the particle-gas heat and mass transfer processes, as
535 well as the enhanced char combustion model, thereby providing a more accurate representation of
536 biomass particle behavior within the burner⁶⁰. As observed by Bonefacic et al.¹⁵, considering the
537 geometric shape of biomass particles, in comparison with other simplified biomass particle models,
538 significantly improves the mixing with air, alters the initiation point and rate of volatile release, and
539 ultimately influences the extent of char combustion.

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Fig. 17 Oxygen concentration distribution distribution along the burner centreline

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Fig. 18 Temperature distribution along the burner centreline

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Fig. 19 Particle burnout distribution along the burner centreline

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Fig. 20 Volatile distribution of particles along the centre line of the burner

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549 3.3 Design of the co-firing burner

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The burner design employed in this study features a bottom secondary air inlet and a circumferential natural gas burner surrounding the biomass burner. Introducing secondary air at the bottom extends the residence time of the cylindrical biomass particles in the natural gas flame, thereby reducing the residual biomass carbon content. However, a comparison of the four model scenarios revealed that the unburned biomass particles had difficulty altering their trajectory, and ultimately, they exited the burner as ash. These particles tended to accumulate at the bottom of the burner, resulting in incomplete biomass combustion. Consequently, the biomass particle burnout and combustion rates within the burner are crucial factors⁹. Neglecting the influence of non-spherical biomass particles on motion and combustion therefore causes many large biomass particles to settle at the bottom of the burner before ignition, with no opportunity to change their downward trajectory for reignition. Even when considering the novel aerodynamic forces and combustion optimisation for cylindrical particles, achieving complete burnout in co-firing burners, as observed for particle 0 in case 4 (see Fig.), remains challenging.

563 The main reason is that changes in biomass particle size, particularly an increase in particle
564 diameter, negatively impact the burnout rate, leading to incomplete combustion. Gera et al.⁶¹
565 similarly pointed out that indicated varying degrees of influence of the high-aspect-ratio biomass
566 particles on carbon burnout, underscoring their significance in determining the particle trajectory,
567 residence time, and carbon burnout rate. To more effectively improve the utilization of large
568 biomass particles during co-firing, the burner structure can be optimized. For instance, a
569 configuration can be employed in which a natural gas burner is arranged in a circular pattern at the
570 bottom, while a secondary air inlet surrounds the biomass injector in the middle section. Although
571 large biomass particles that are not fully combusted may fall to the bottom of the burner, they can
572 continue to burn with the support of the gas flame at the base. During the process of particle mass
573 loss, the use of a novel cylindrical particle model, combined with a comprehensive consideration of
574 various aerodynamic forces such as drag, lift, pressure gradient force, virtual mass force, and
575 torque-induced rotational motion, along with corrections for particle geometry within the
576 combustion model, allows for effective optimization of large biomass particle trajectories in
577 numerical simulations. This approach provides practical benefits for improving burnout efficiency
578 in the direct co-firing of biomass in coal-fired boilers under industrial conditions⁶².

579 In Fig. 15, the stream of particle No.16 from case 4 exhibits significantly earlier
580 devolatilisation than those in cases 1 and 2, and this is accompanied by a faster particle mass loss.
581 Notably, the novel aerodynamics and advanced combustion models throughout the combustion
582 process ensured that the biomass trajectories predominantly followed the central line of the burner,
583 with only a small fraction of the particles falling to the bottom. In addition, the provision of
584 additional appropriate oxygen leads to a more complete combustion of the biomass particles. Figure

585 16 demonstrates that all particles No. 20 in stream of case 4 exited the burner from the middle,
586 indicating the complete burnout of biomass particles as they exited in the form of ash.

587 Finally, data were collected regarding the average residence time, maximum particle
588 temperature, and overall burnout rate of various typical particles in the burner, as listed in Table 5.
589 In a 10 m-long burner, the differences among the four cases numerical simulation results were
590 significant. As mentioned earlier, after applying the more comprehensive novel aerodynamic and
591 optimized combustion models based on the shape of non-spherical biomass particles, case 4 shows
592 higher residence time and particle temperature compared to the other cases. Compared with case 1,
593 the average particle residence time increased by 20.21%, while the average particle temperature
594 increased by 28.31%. Importantly, longer particle residence times and higher particle temperatures
595 facilitated the complete combustion of biomass particles under sufficient oxygen conditions. In the
596 case of large particles (particles NO.0, NO.4, NO.7, and NO.10), particular improvements in the
597 biomass burnout rates were observed. More specifically, for case 4, increases of 10.8%, 15.2%,
598 73.4%, and 59.84%, respectively, were obtained for these particles compared with the
599 corresponding results for case 1. Thus, if oxygen supply is not limited, the factors considered in the
600 novel model can significantly enhance the burnout rate of large biomass particles.

601 Overall, comprehensively considering the non-spherical effects of biomass particles is crucial
602 for achieving an improved understanding of the combustion process for different biomass particle
603 sizes. This also provides an essential reference for determining the appropriate size standards for the
604 co-firing of biomass specimens. Accurate modeling of the trajectory and combustion process of
605 biomass particles is crucial for the future design of biomass burners. It directly determines the
606 effectiveness of biomass utilization in the optimization of coal-fired boilers with direct combustion
607 coupling.

608

Table 5 Representative particle information

Group [No.]	0	4	7	10	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
Case 1/Time (s)	0.501	0.505	0.512	0.519	0.532	0.537	0.549	0.576	0.580	0.697	0.538	0.528	0.705
Temperature (K)	551.5	609.9	1177.1	1283.5	1901.9	1905.4	1908.6	1930.1	1934.9	1934.9	1935.4	1944.4	1948.6
Burnout (%)	0	0	18.23	31.84	71.67	71.67	71.67	71.67	71.67	71.67	72.11	72.28	82.39
Case 2/Time (s)	0.529	0.546	0.571	0.591	0.628	0.628	0.622	0.615	0.617	0.631	0.643	0.653	0.657
Temperature (K)	576.7	657.3	1652.0	1801.3	1925.6	1926.9	1927.5	1937.5	1933.6	1929.8	1934.4	1935.2	1956.7
Burnout (%)	0	0	55.14	72.28	76.67	78.67	78.67	78.67	78.67	78.99	78.43	78.66	85.63
Case 3/Time (s)	0.598	0.561	0.666	0.646	0.711	0.708	0.702	0.712	0.705	0.760	0.580	0.639	0.758
Temperature (K)	644.7	664.0	1846.7	1950.9	1981.2	1981.4	1982.8	1992.8	1989.7	1956.1	1972.6	1976.6	1976.6
Burnout (%)	1.837	5.53	81.68	81.68	81.68	81.68	81.68	81.7	81.7	82.03	82.77	82.77	91.15
Case 4/Time (s)	0.591	0.557	0.6593	0.640	0.7153	0.709	0.711	0.728	0.719	0.762	0.568	0.628	0.7626
Temperature (K)	670.5	694.8	2175.3	2118.9	2203.7	2207.1	2229.7	2228.5	2241.4	2202.5	2298.5	2196.6	3434.8
Burnout (%)	10.8	15.2	91.68	91.68	89.68	89.68	89.68	89.7	89.7	89.58	89.85	89.66	95.01

609

610 4 Conclusions

611 This study significantly improves the existing modeling framework for dilute multiphase
612 particle motion by accurately capturing the dynamics and combustion behavior of cylindrical straw
613 biomass particles in coal-fired boilers under direct co-firing conditions. The proposed novel model
614 incorporates more generalized correlations derived from our previous particle-resolved direct
615 numerical simulations. Based on these, a robust and reliable model has been developed that couples
616 translational and rotational particle dynamics with an optimized combustion model, enabling
617 high-fidelity simulation and optimization of biomass suspension combustion. Numerical
618 simulations conducted on a 10 meter long biomass co-firing burner validate the accuracy and wide
619 applicability of the cylindrical particle motion and combustion model. The main conclusions are as
620 follows:

621 (1) Accurate prediction of the motion and combustion behavior of biomass particles requires
622 consideration of their true non-spherical shape and size. The proposed model effectively couples
623 particle translational motion (including drag, additional lift induced by non-sphericity, virtual mass

624 force, pressure gradient force, and gravity) with torque driven rotational motion, allowing for
625 precise trajectory prediction. Furthermore, by incorporating sphericity factor corrections into the
626 combustion model, the framework more realistically reproduces the co-firing of biomass and
627 natural gas.

628 (2) Compared with conventional models, the novel model increases the average particle
629 residence time by 20.21% and the average particle temperature by 28.31%. This more rapid heating
630 process, combined with extended residence time, promotes enhanced volatile release and char
631 oxidation, leading to greater mass loss and making particle conversion behavior and combustion
632 performance more representative of real-world scenarios.

633 The developed novel model demonstrates strong potential for future applications in tracking
634 the behavior of non-spherical biomass particles in co-firing with coal. It offers valuable support for
635 boiler condition diagnosis and operational optimization. Nevertheless, further investigation is
636 needed into the effects of particle collisions on motion and combustion behavior, especially under
637 high biomass concentration conditions.

638

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645

646 **Declaration of Competing Interest**

647 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
648 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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